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COLCHICINE-INDUCED VARIATIONS IN COWPEA (*VIGNA UNGUICULATA* L. WALP)

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ABSTRACT: Cowpea is very important in the tropical and sub-tropical regions of Africa where it serves as a source of protein for the local population coupled with its ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen. Induced mutation has been successful in many crop species but least applied in legumes like cowpea. Experiment was conducted on colchicine induced variations in cowpea by exposing the apical shoots of seedlings of two cowpea accessions (NG07 and NG08) to 0.2% colchicine in semi-solid agar. Semi-solid agar proved to be an effective medium of applying colchicine to apical shoots of cowpea seedlings. Traits like plant height, number of pods per plant and seeds per pod were reduced by colchicine treatment compared to control. Terminal leaflet length and number of nodes were enhanced by colchicine treatment compared to control and seed weight was significantly enhanced in both accessions compared to the control. There were contradictory responses to colchicine treatment between the two accessions for peduncle length, number of primary branches and pod length, indicating response to be genotype specific within a species. Colchicine caused noticeable differences in qualitative traits like twining tendency, plant pigmentation, testa texture and leaf colour for both accessions. The range of variations observed from this study indicates a better possibility of genetic breeding through this approach.

Key words: Colchicine, semi-solid agar, cowpea, traits, accessions

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INTRODUCTION

The position of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*), as a source of protein for resource poor people of Africa and other parts of the world, has been established, and cannot be overemphasized. Its high protein content of about 25% makes it an important grain legume; being alternative to animal protein [1,2]. Nigeria accounts for the largest amount of cowpea production in the world, followed by Niger, Mali, Burkina Faso and Senegal [3]. The improvement of cowpea over the years has been based principally on hybridization and selection (conventional breeding techniques).

These have resulted in not much improvement due to the fact that these techniques are laborious and time consuming. Therefore, the use of mutation breeding technique, which can induce diversity of quantitative and qualitative traits in crops, is desirable [4].

Induced mutations have been successful at generating variability, and hence improved yield and yield components of various crop species, such as barley [5], cotton [6] and rice [7]; *Vigna unguiculata* [8], *Vigna mungo* [9] and *Sorghum bicolor* [10]; yet it has been least applied in grain legumes [11]. According to Micke et al. [12], only eight out of 1000 improved mutant varieties of different crops released up to 1989 in over 48 countries were cowpea.

The present study were to investigate the effects of colchicine on both the quantitative and qualitative traits of two cowpea accessions and to test the effectiveness of semi-solid agar as a medium of applying colchicine to apical shoots of cowpea seedlings.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two accessions of cowpea used in this study were collected from the National Centre for Genetic Resources and Biotechnology (NACGRAB) Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. These accessions are NG/SA/07/1066-2 and NG/SA/07/0008, coded NG07 and NG08 respectively for easy presentation of results.

Each accession of cowpea was planted in germination baskets of about 15000cm³, filled with sandy loamy soil at The Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology Laboratory, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko, Ondo State, Nigeria. Sixty seeds were planted per plastic basket, which were later thinned to 50 per basket after emergence. Two baskets were sown with seeds from each accession, while each basket of an accession was regarded as a treatment and there were 4 baskets in total. When seedlings were one week old, seedlings in an individual plastic basket per accession were either treated with four applications of 0.2% colchicine or left untreated (control). Colchicine was diluted in distilled water to concentration of 0.2% with 0.28g agar and kept in oven at 60°C for 60 minutes according to Jones et al. [13] with a little modification. A single drop of warm colchicine suspension was then pipetted on top of the apical bud of each seedling to cover the emerging shoot (Figure 1). Subsequent applications were made once per day for 3days. Baskets with seedlings were kept at the laboratory till the end of treatments. One week after treatment, seedlings were transferred to the field prior analysis. Seedlings were transplanted on the Experimental Field of the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba Akoko, Ondo State (Latitude 7.28°N, Longitude 5.44°E, Altitude 423m above sea level), and this was during the raining season of 2013.

Spacing was 50cm between seedlings on each ridge of 5m long, and 1m between ridges per treatment per replication for each accession. 10 seedlings were planted per accession per treatment per replication and total number of plants in the field was 160 in total of 4 replications. The experimental design was Randomized Complete Design (RCD). Data on plant height (cm) was recorded from week two after treatment (one week after transplanting) to week four (five weeks after transplanting), some quantitative traits and all qualitative traits were recorded at eight weeks after transplanting and the remaining data (on yield) were recorded at maturity, and all were subjected to statistical analysis. Means, Standard error and ANOVA were computed for quantitative traits while means were only computed for qualitative traits. The quantitative traits recorded were; Plant height (cm), recorded at week 1, 2, 3 and 4 after transplanting; Number of primary branches and Number of nodes on main stem at week 8; Peduncle length (cm), Number of pods per peduncle, Pod length (cm) recorded at maturity; Number of seeds per pod and 100-Seed weight (g), recorded by randomly weighing 100 seeds per replication per accession per treatment were also recorded at maturity. The qualitative parameters considered were; Growth pattern: 1, determinate; 2, indeterminate. Twining tendency: 3, slight; 5, intermediate; 7, pronounced. Plant pigmentation: 3, moderate; 7, extensive. Terminal leaflet shape: 1, globose; 2, sub globose; 3 sub hastate; 4, hastate. Plant hairiness: 3, glabrescent; 5, short appressed hairs; 7, pubescent to hirsute. Pod attachment to peduncle: 3, pendant; 5, 30-90° down from erect; 7, erect. Pod curvature: 0, straight; 3, slight curved; 5, curved 7, coiled. Immature pod pigmentation: 0, none; 1, pigmented tip; 2 pigmented suture; 5 uniformly pigmented. Seed shape: 1, kidney; 2, ovoid; 3, crowder; 4, globose; 5, rhomboid. Testa texture: 3, smooth to rough; 7 rough to wrinkle. Leaf colour: 3, pale green; 5, intermediate green; 7, dark green. Flower colour: 1, white; 2, violet; 3, mauve-pink; 4, other. The qualitative traits were scored according to method described in the Cowpea Descriptor of The International Board for Plant Genetic Resources (IBPGR).

RESULTS

For more than two weeks after treatments, there was inhibition of growth on all the treated plants, hence their failures to initiate trifoliate leaves (Figure 2), though normal growth and development were later resumed by the treated plants. Plant height for the treated plant remained lower than that of the control for more than four weeks after treatments (Figure 3). The highest plant height (22.7cm) at week four after transplanting was recorded for NG07 (control) while the lowest height (18.88cm) was recorded for NG08 (treated). Overall, all the treated plants of same accession had lower height (10.21cm and 19.09cm – 22.13cm and 18.88cm) compared to their respective control (13.78cm and 10.79cm – 22.7cm and 21.03cm) from first week of transplanting to week four, though the treated plants were already catching up at week four after transplanting (Figure 3).

Figure 1: Treated shoot of the cowpea plant

Figure 2: Trifoliate leaf on each of the control seedlings (A and B) and absence of trifoliate leaves on treated seedlings (C and D) two weeks after colchicine treatments.

Terminal leaflet length recorded at week 4 showed the treated plants of the two accessions having longer lengths (4.14cm and 2.42cm) than the control (2.85cm and 2.29cm) (Table 1). Overall longest terminal leaflet length for control was still maintained by NG07 while NG08 had the lowest terminal leaflet length for control. Number of primary branches recorded at 8th week after treatment was highest (5.88) for NG08 (control); followed by its treated plants (5.69). Overall, primary branches of both treated and control of NG08 were found to be higher than that of the treated and control of NG07. While NG08 had higher number of branches for control plants compared to its treated plants, NG07 had the value for its treated plants (5.25) to be higher than control (4.31) (Table 1). Number of nodes on main stem was higher for both treated plants among the two accessions (4.55 and 4.08), with NG07 having the highest, compared to the control (3.08 and 3.16) which were lower, and NG07 having the lowest number of nodes (Table 1). Peduncle length was highest (12.03cm) for NG08 for control, followed by its treated plants (9.88cm). Both the treated plants and the control plants of NG07 had lower peduncle length, which were 9.14cm and 8.50cm respectively (Table 1).

Number of pods per plant was highest (24.25) for treated NG07 compared to its control (24.00), while the control of NG08 had higher number of pods (23.25) compared to its treated plants (Table 2). Accession NG08 had highest pod length (7.55cm) for treated plants, followed by its control (6.6cm) with accession NG07 showing values in opposite direction, as its control had higher pod length (5.37) compared to its treated plants (4.73). Overall, pods were shorter in accession NG07 (Table 1). Number of seeds per pod was highest (11.75) for NG08 (control), followed by 11.10 for NG07 (control). The treated plants of both accessions had lower number of seeds per pod (9.83 and 10.50) compared to their respective controls (Table 1). 100-seed weight was lower in the controls of both accessions (38.5g and 35.9g) compared to the values of their treated plants (42.8g and 44.7g). Overall highest seed weight was recorded for treated NG08 and lowest was recorded for control NG07 (Table 1).

Table 1: Mean values and standard error of quantitative traits of the treated accessions

Treatment	NG07		NG08		NG07		NG08	
Terminal Leaflet Length (cm)				Number of Pods per Plant				
Control	2.85	0.30	2.29	0.28	25.00	1.48	23.25	2.25
Treated	3.44	0.28	2.42	0.29	24.25	1.71	19.25	2.32
Difference	+0.59		+0.13		-0.75		-4.00	
Number of Primary Branches				Pod Length (cm)				
Control	4.31	0.18	5.88	0.70	5.37	0.61	6.60	0.68
Treated	5.25	0.13	5.69	0.60	4.73	0.47	7.55	0.91
Difference	+0.94		-0.19		-0.64		+0.95	
Number of Nodes on Main Stem				Number of Seeds per Pod				
Control	3.08	0.38	3.16	0.47	11.10	0.75	11.75	1.12
Treated	4.55	0.44	4.08	0.60	9.83	1.23	10.50	2.02
Difference	+1.47		+0.92		-1.27		-1.25	
Peduncle Length (cm)				100-Seed Weight (g)				
Control	9.14	0.39	9.88	0.85	38.5	1.20	35.9	1.10
Treated	8.50	0.68	12.03	0.71	42.8	2.00	44.7	3.00
Difference	-0.64		+2.15		+4.30		+8.80	

Analysis of variance revealed number of replications to be highly significant for plant height (cm), 100-seed weight (g) and pod length (cm). Replication was not significant for other studied parameters. The treatment effect was significant for 100-seed weight (g) and pod length (cm), while it was not significant for other studied parameters. Effect of accession was highly significant for 100-seed weight (g), but not significant for other parameters. Colchicine level was highly significant for pod length (cm), while not being significant for other studied parameters. Accession by colchicine effect was found to be non-significant for all the studied parameters (Table 2).

Figure 3: Plant height from week 1 to week 4 after transplanting

The values for the twelve qualitative characters are presented in table 3. Treatment did not cause any changes in growth pattern of the two accessions. Twining tendency was slight and pronounced for control and treated plants respectively for NG07, while it is pronounced and intermediate for control and treated plants respectively for NG08. Plant pigmentation was moderate for the control of both accessions, while it was extensive for the treated plants of both accessions. There were no changes between control and treated plants of both accessions for terminal leaflet shape (all globose), plant hairiness (all short appressed hairs), pod attachment to peduncle (all 30-90° down from erect), immature pod pigmentation (all pigmented sutures), pod curvature (all straight), flower colour (all violet) and seed shape (all kidney). Testa texture was smooth to rough for both controls of the two accessions while it was rough to wrinkle in both the treated plants of the two accessions. Leaf colour was pale green for both accessions (control) while it was dark green for both accessions (treated).

Table 2: Mean square values for the quantitative traits from analysis of variance

Sv	Df	PH	TML	NPB	NNP	PEDL	NPP	PODL	NSP	100-SW
Rp	3	214.53**	0.23 ^{ns}	0.59 ^{ns}	0.88 ^{ns}	9.50 ^{ns}	23.90 ^{ns}	13.00**	15.98 ^{ns}	0.94**
Trt	3	5.29 ^{ns}	1.89 ^{ns}	1.94 ^{ns}	1.35 ^{ns}	9.42 ^{ns}	21.73 ^{ns}	6.25*	1.12 ^{ns}	0.63*
Ac	1	8.80 ^{ns}	1.84 ^{ns}	0.56 ^{ns}	4.02 ^{ns}	2.30 ^{ns}	14.10 ^{ns}	0.02 ^{ns}	2.25 ^{ns}	1.71**
Cl	1	6.18 ^{ns}	2.82 ^{ns}	3.99 ^{ns}	0.01 ^{ns}	18.15*	33.10 ^{ns}	16.40**	0.11 ^{ns}	0.002 ^{ns}
Ac X Cl	1	0.87 ^{ns}	1.02 ^{ns}	1.27 ^{ns}	0.04 ^{ns}	7.81 ^{ns}	17.99 ^{ns}	2.25 ^{ns}	1.00 ^{ns}	0.19 ^{ns}
E	9	20.54	0.61	4.11	1.23	2.62	16.73	0.93	9.29	0.09

** - Significant at 1% level; * - Significant at 5% level; ns – Not significant; Sv – Source of variation; Rp – Replication; Trt – Treatment; Ac – Accession; Cl – Colchicine treatment; E – Error; Df – Degree of freedom; PH – Plant Height; TML – Terminal Leaflet Length; NPB – Number of Primary Branches; NNP – Number of Nodes per Plant; PEDL – Peduncle Length; NPP – Number of Pods per Plant; PODL – Pod Length; NSP – Number of seeds per Pod; SW – Seed Weight

Table 3: Mean Values of 12 Qualitative Traits for the Control (T1) and Treated (T2) Accessions of Cowpea

Accessions	GTP		TWT		PLP		TLS		PLH		PAP	
	T1	T2										
NG07	1	1	3	7	3	7	1	1	5	5	5	5
NG08	1	1	7	5	3	7	1	1	5	5	5	5
	IMP		SDS		TET		LFC		POC		FLC	
	T1	T2										
NG07	2	2	1	1	3	7	3	7	0	0	2	2
NG08	2	2	1	1	3	7	3	7	0	0	2	2

GTP – Growth pattern; TWT – Twining tendency; PLP – Plant pigmentation; TLS – Terminal leaflet shape; PLH – Plant hairiness; PAP – Pod attachment to peduncle; IMP – Immature pod pigmentation; SDS – Seed shape; TET – Testa texture; LFC – Leaf colour; POC – Pod curvature; FC – Flower colour

DISCUSSIONS

Semi-solid agar used in this experiment as a medium of applying colchicine to apical shoots of cowpea seedlings proved to be effective, as the drops of the mixture rested, solidified and stayed on the emerging shoot of each seedling, effecting good contact between the colchicine and shoot and persisted for more than three days after treatment before breaking down. These observations have also been reported by Jones et al. 2008 on induction of polyploidy on *Rhododendron* seedlings with agar-orizalin mixture.

The wide ranges of variability observed in this study have been reported by many workers on different crop species. Growth inhibition after mutagenic treatment has been a known phenomenon in plants [4, 13, 15, 16, 17]. Reduced growth rate after colchicine treatments has been linked to signs of polyploidy and successful treatments of colchicine. According to Ndukwu and Obute, [16], the slow growth could be a result of the treatment being an assault to the apical region of the plants. It usually results in the disturbance of natural rate of cell cycle thereby affecting overall growth; while death of seedlings of *Licopersicum esculentum* has been linked to clumping of chromosome in the meristem [18].

The longer leaflet length for the treated plants of both accessions may be a useful trait for breeding, as it may lead to increase in the net photosynthetic area which may lead to increase in photosynthetic assimilates going into grains as a positive effect of seed yield, being similar conclusions reached in many crop species for mutagenesis [19, 20, 21, 22]. Other noticeable leaf variations like darker green leaf color of treated plants of both accessions, may be as a result of higher level of chlorophyll present in the treated plants, which is similar to what was obtained by Babu et al. [23], who explained that changes in the net photosynthetic rate and leaf area have been found to be correlated with chlorophyll a/b. Colchicine has also been found to behave like stress factor which may alter the chlorophyll content of leaf segments, however, this variation may not affect the growth of mutant. The increased in branching of the treated plants is in agreement with [15, 16] coupled with increased nodes reported; it is an indication of probable bushy habit induction ability of colchicine treatment. The significant increases in peduncle length (cm) and pod length (cm) for NG08 for treated plants, negates the results for accession NG07, which indicates that response to mutagenic treatments may be genotype specific within same species. The decrease in pod length (cm) of the treated NG07, number of pods per plant, and number of seed per pod of both accessions all contradict the results of Odeigah, [11] on M1 generation of cowpea but similar to what was obtained by Kumar et al. 2009, who showed that reduction in pod number may be as a result of inhibiting action of enzymes, changes in enzymatic activities and toxicity of the mutagen on these traits, while reduced seed yield can be attributed to high seed sterility and reduced pod number, also as consequences of physiological and biochemical disturbances in the development of plants [24] resulting from mutagenic treatment. In conclusion, taking all characters into consideration, there is an observable relatively high level of dissimilarities among the two accessions as a result of colchicine treatment. This indicates a better possibility of genetic breeding through this approach. This study also revealed that some morphological traits (quantitative and qualitative), were more efficient at discriminating between the accessions for mutagenic treatments studies than others. Although some morphological characters were enhanced by colchicine treatment in *Vigna unguiculata*, colchicine failed to increase the number of pods and seeds, even though; these properties might be the most important targets in cowpea.

Nevertheless, colchicine treatment increased the seed weight significantly in all accessions which is a positive development. However, further studies are being carried out to elucidate the effects of colchicine on agronomic traits, by raising M2 to M4 populations from seeds developed from this research, bearing in mind that characters that are not expressed now may be expressed in future generations.

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